

THE ARROWS PROJECT FOR UNDERWATER ARCHAEOLOGY*

IL PROGETTO ARROWS PER L'ARCHEOLOGIA SUBACQUEA

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ARROWS è l'acronimo di ARchaeological ROBot systems for the World's Seas. Il progetto, iniziato nel settembre 2012, è finanziato dal 7° programma quadro della Commissione Europea nell'ambito della call ENV-2012, challenge 6.2-6, dedicata allo "Sviluppo di tecnologie avanzate e strumenti per la mappatura, la diagnosi, lo scavo e la protezione di siti archeologici sottomarini e costieri".

Il consorzio ARROWS comprende 10 partner di 5 paesi diversi con competenze sia accademiche che industriali nei settori dell'archeologia subacquea, dell'ingegneria oceanica, della robotica e della visione computazionale. I costi delle ricerche archeologiche subacquee effettuate con l'utilizzo di una nave di ricerca e Operatori Tecnici Subacquei e/o veicoli robotici teleoperati (ROV) sono molto elevati (fino a € 50.000 al giorno) e ben oltre i budget di molte istituzioni di ricerca/tutela del patrimonio archeologico.

Ridurre il costo delle operazioni subacquee correlate all'archeologia subacquea è un passo importante ed imprescindibile per la tutela del patrimonio culturale sommerso. La sfida lanciata dal Progetto ARROWS è lo sviluppo di nuove tecnologie e l'adattamento di altre, sviluppate nel settore militare ed in quello dello sfruttamento degli idrocarburi, al fine di realizzare veicoli sottomarini autonomi (Autonomous Underwater Vehicle - AUV) idonei ad effettuare indagini archeologiche in diversi ambienti marini. Saranno utilizzati due diversi siti di sperimentazione, uno sul Baltico ed uno nell'arcipelago delle Egadi.

Keywords: Underwater Cultural Heritage, Fast Horizontal Surveys, Accurate Geo-referencing, Mapping, Monitoring, Good Practices for Underwater Archaeology.

Fig. 2 - A historical wreck still to be inspected in the Baltic Sea.

On the opposite page, Fig. 1 - Wreck of probable frigate in the Baltic Sea as seen by a side-scan sonar.

Fig. 3 - The "Rostro di Cecè," a ram, belonging to a Roman ship, found near Capo Grosso di Levanzo (Egadi archipelago, Sicily) the 11th August 2011.

ARROWS is the acronym for ARchaeological RO-bot systems for the World's Seas¹. The project, started in September 2012, is funded by the EU in the framework of the FP7 call ENV-2012, challenge 6.2-6, devoted to "Development of advanced technologies and tools for mapping, diagnosing, excavating, and securing underwater and coastal archaeological sites". The ARROWS consortium comprises expertise from underwater archaeology, underwater engineering, robotics, image processing and recognition from academia and industry. 10 partners from 5 different Countries are involved.

The cost of underwater archaeological investigations using a research ship with skilled human operators and/or Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) is high (up to €50k per day) and beyond the range of many archaeological research institutions. *Reducing the cost of underwater archaeological operations* is an important issue to address in advancing the knowledge of our cultural heritage. The challenge faced by ARROWS is to generate and adapt existing technologies in the field of military, security and offshore oil and gas applications, in order to develop user-friendly and low cost Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) technologies for archaeological investigation in different sea environments. Two different demonstration sites will be used, one in the Baltic Sea and one in the Egadi archipelago (Sicily). A wreck still to be explored and classified in the Baltic sea is shown in *fig. 1*. An ancient ram found in the Egadi Archipelago is shown in *fig. 2*.

Some of the partners of ARROWS have been partners of

the THESAURUS project² (funded by Regione Toscana from 2011 to 2013. THESAURUS stands for "Tecnica per l'Esplorazione Sottomarina Archeologica mediante l'Utilizzo di Robot aUtonomi in Sciami". The main outcome of the THESAURUS project is a class of moderate-cost AUVs named "Typhoon" capable of operation in deep sea up to 300m. Three Typhoon AUVs with different sensor equipment on board have been built and tested at sea (see *figs. 3 and 4*). For a complete overview of the THESAURUS project see the official website of the project³ and the associated YouTube channel⁴.

The three Typhoons are equipped with GPS (for accurate surface localization) and acoustic modems in order to allow underwater communication and cooperation. One of the Typhoons is equipped with a USBL, an acoustic device allowing to measure the positions of other AUVs. With the USBL-equipped vehicle navigating in surface (i.e. with GPS signal available), quite accurate localization of underwater sites and artefacts and geo-referencing of images and sonograms is possible (see *figs. 5 and 6*).

The THESAURUS experience has shown that developing and operating moderate-cost AUVs is possible since the logistics of the Typhoon vehicles is similar to that of a sailboat (see *fig. 7*) and a support ship is not necessary as it happens for ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicle).

Two important lessons have been learnt from the THESAURUS project:

- The weight of each Typhoon in air is in the range of 180kg and its length is 3.8m, so it is necessary

Fig. 4 - The Typhoon design and embodiment.

¹ ARROWS 2012.
² ALLOTTA et al. 2012.
³ THESAURUS 2011.
⁴ THESAURUS 2013.

Fig. 5 - The Typhoon ready for deployment in Livorno harbour.

Fig. 6 - The Typhoon looking for a II World War wreck during tests in Livorno the 27th August 2013.

Fig. 7 - Communication/cooperation among AUVs.

to reduce the weight and length of vehicles in order to drastically simplify the logistics and the operational costs and increase portability.

- In order to allow archaeologists to directly operate AUVs it is necessary to make them user-friendly by simplifying the human-machine interface.

To reduce weight, length and logistic costs of AUVs as well as the complexity of their operation are specific objectives of the ARROWS project.

The challenge

ARROWS focuses on providing new methods for mapping, diagnosis, and excavation. Specific methodologies for rapid on-site analysis will also be devised and developed. The aim of the project is to identify the archaeologists' requirements throughout the investigation, identify problems and propose solutions with technological readiness levels that predict their maturation for exploitation within 3-5 years. In particular some of the expected results are:

- fast and low cost horizontal surveys of large areas using customised AUVs with multimodal sensing;

- high quality maps from better image reconstruction methods and improved location accuracy of AUVs;
- shipwreck penetration and internal mapping using small low cost vehicles localising using fixed pingers;
- mixed reality environments for virtual exploration of archaeological sites;
- monitoring changes via back-to-the-site missions;
- training archaeologists to use new equipment and techniques.

Methodology

The project relies on an Archaeological Advisory Group (AAG). The AAG is co-ordinated by the Archaeological Director and reports in to the Project Steering Board. The role of the AAG is to steer the work of engineers by providing strategic non-executive input to the project, but involves external influences from the application community. It comprises archaeologists from inside and outside the consortium, supported by WP leaders and the Project Co-ordinator. Its role is to review project progress from an application perspective, and to advise on future plans, to maximise relevance and opportunity for the project's technology. It will also play a pivotal role supporting the development of standard procedures, training of archaeologists and dissemination of project results and technology to the Archaeological community. The AAG meets possibly aligned with EC review meetings and as often as necessary on an ad hoc basis as required by the chair. The technologies will be developed using agile development methods comprising rapid cycles of testing and comparison against the archaeologists' requirements. The archaeological activity will be carried out through four phases:

- Mapping: The first phase is the search for histori-

Fig. 8 - Acoustic communication and localization tests with three Typhoons in Roffia (Pisa, Italy) 31th August 2013.

cal sites, such as ancient wrecks and isolated items, by means of systematic surveys;

- Diagnosis: Return to the site to confirm findings from mapping by closer analysis;
- Cleaning: After locating a site of interest, small cleaning activities will be performed by vehicles controlled from the surface if approved by a team of expert archaeologists;
- Analysis: The last phase is the categorization of

the findings and their interpretation in the wider historical context.

The research and cleaning systems and methodologies will comply with the UNESCO Convention for the protection of Underwater Cultural Heritage. Training workshops will be organized to illustrate how to operate a system including AUVs with complementary sensor equipment.

Fig. 9 - Preliminary design of the MARTA (MARine Tool for Archaeology) AUV and of a biomimetic turtle-inspired robot for modern wreck penetration

Project's outcome

The outcome of the project will consist of a smart system composed of AUVs able to operate together on a submersed archaeological site. They will be designed and developed to comply with archaeologists' specifications: low cost, portable, user friendly and modular. A preliminary design of novel AUVs, based on experiences from previous projects, has been performed and prototypes will be ready by the beginning of 2014 (see *fig. 8*).

Training the archaeologists in the use of the new equipment and techniques, possibly for independent use, will be one of the main results of the project. Although the ARROWS project is specifically tailored to answer the needs of underwater archaeologists, the technologies developed are expected to be useful in the other areas of human activities such as environmental monitoring and geological investigation.

Conclusion

The ARROWS project aims at providing technologies for the preservation of underwater cultural heritage. Archaeologists from inside and outside the ARROWS consortium are actively involved in the definition of the research streamlines in order to ensure that systems and methodologies comply with the UNESCO Convention for the protection of Underwater Cultural Heritage. ARROWS is expected to propose and demonstrate solutions with technological readiness levels that predict their maturation for exploitation within 3-5 years from the conclusion of the project in September 2015.

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